

A national assessment of park quality across Great Britain

Jess Hepburn^{*1}, Fiona Caryl^{†1}, Jonathan Olsen^{^1} and Rich Mitchell⁺¹

¹ MRC/CSO Social and Public Health Sciences Unit, University of Glasgow

GISRUK 2024

Summary

A national audit of park quality (and qualities) is important to understand influences, distribution, and the impact these may have on the demographics and health of the population across Great Britain. For this project, we objectively measure park quality at a GB-wide national level. We completed exploratory analysis with future work plans that will allow us to understand distinct park typology and national distribution.

KEYWORDS: Greenspace, park quality, deprivation, national scale

1. Introduction

Greenspace quality is important to consider as an assortment of research has found that it is positively associate to health and wellbeing (Bowler et al., 2010), with larger, greener, and more active public open spaces linked to better health (Paquet et al., 2013). Studies, on a local level, have also found that the quality of greenspace, can be more beneficial to individuals than the quantity of greenspace (van Dillen et al., 2012; Feng and Astell-Burt, 2017; Francis et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2021). Nevertheless, there exists no unified definition for greenspace or park quality, with the range of research in this area being broad and varied. Existing evaluations of greenspace quality predominantly rely on subjective field surveys and questionnaires conducted in local environments. These surveys, while valuable at the city scale, pose challenges due to their lack of reproducibility and labour-intensive and expensive nature, it is therefore challenging to systematically audit all greenspaces within a national geographic extent (Brindley et al., 2019).

For this project, we objectively measure park quality across GB. The objectivity means that we can do this at a nationwide scale, with minimal subjective bias compared to local level park quality audits with surveys/questionnaires. Objective measures were calculated for every park in Great Britain (defined by Ordnance Survey (OS) Open Greenspace (2021), where function was Public Park or Garden). With some measures considering neighbouring areas, such as toilets, cafes, and public transport within 100m of the park edge. We compared park measures across Functional Urban Areas (FUAs) for between-city evaluation given OS Greenspace data are restricted to urban areas. In addition, cities were compared through calculating the Relative Index of Inequality of population social distribution and geographic location (North/South). This allowed us to examine park quality differences across GB and association with location and inequality. A national audit of parks is important to understand influences, distribution, and the impact these may have on the demographics and health of the population across GB. Knowing where 'high' quality and 'low' quality parks are located will also be able to guide policy and decisions on allocation and design of funds, and improvement or regeneration of parks.

2. Methodology

2.1. Park Quality Measures

Park quality measures were calculated for every park across GB (n = 11,449). A park is defined by OS

*Jessica.Hepburn@Glasgow.ac.uk

†Fiona.Caryl@Glasgow.ac.uk

^Jonathan.Olsen@glasgow.ac.uk

+Rich.Mitchell@Glasgow.ac.uk

Open Greenspace (2021), where function was defined as Public Park or Garden. This is the most extensive database of Greenspace which is represented across all the devolved nations and updated regularly. This dataset is only for urban areas, which is why FUAs are used in our investigation. In addition, data is sourced from; OS Points of Interest (2020), Sustrans National Cycle Network (2015), Copernicus High Resolution Layers (2018), UKCEH Land Cover Map: Land Parcels (2020), to characterise the physical manmade features of the park and natural biodiversity features. Data on the size and shape is also calculated, using the modified compactness index (CI) designed to provide an area-independent measure of a shape's geometric complexity. In addition to absolute value of qualities (such as the number of sports facilities), binary values for qualities have also been calculated, which are useful for analysis.

2.2. Park Quality comparisons across Functional Urban Areas

To define urban areas to compare for analyses, FUAs boundaries were used. These are created by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), to generate a harmonised definition of cities and their areas of influence for international comparisons (Dijkstra et al., 2019). These are a global geography, meaning that future work using FUAs could be transferred for an international comparison, making them a justifiable choice in our analysis. Across GB, there are 86 towns and cities defined as FUAs. As we were interested in sociodemographic data associated with the census, we linked the FUAs with appropriate small area geographies (LSOAs in England and Wales, Datazones in Scotland); however, LSOA boundaries do not fully align with FUA boundaries. Therefore, small area geographies were selected based on whether their centroid intersects the geometry of the FUA. This meant that if there are two FUAs which share a boundary, such as Newcastle upon Tyne and Sunderland, then LSOAs would not be double counted, and would be only associated with one FUA. This outputted a new geography, FUA small-area geographies, which is used throughout this analysis.

Across England, Wales, and Scotland there are calculated measures of the relative deprivation of neighbourhoods for each of the devolved nations; the Indices of Multiple Deprivation (IMD). These separate indices account for the unique policy priorities and data sources in each nation; with each applying slightly different methodology and weighting to the various sociodemographic inputs/indices. Work by Abel et al., (2016) used open census data to produce consistent UK-wide and GB-wide indices of deprivation for small-area statistics (LSOAs and Datazones). These methods were then applied by Parsons (2021), to create both a GB and UK Composite IMD for the year 2020. Using the allocation of LSOA associated with each FUA, the percentage of population within each deprivation quintile was determined; allowing for the Relative Index of Inequality (RII) to be calculated; giving a national picture of deprivation and inequality distribution across the FUAs.

Using the FUAs as a boundary, parks contained within an FUA are allocated; allowing for the quality measures to be summarised. A within selection measure was used as this allows for only parks completely contained within the FUA to be evaluated. Some parks boundaries do overlap the FUA boundary, and are thus excluded, however, this only applies to 2.6% of all GB parks. The categorisation is based on geographical location (North/South) and inequality, based on the RII, FUAs were classed as less deprived population, more deprived population and neutral.

3. Results

After completing exploratory analysis, we focused on park number/size and six distinct park facilities as individual qualities. As shown in **Figure 1** we found that the areas of park per 100,000 people varied across deprivation and regions; with people living in the North on average having access to more area of park than the South; across all levels of deprivation. However, when this was normalised by the total FUA area (i.e., area of park per 100,000 people per 100km²), we found that this swayed the results; with the south having more park area accessible to them. In addition, the North seemed on average to contain a greater number of parks, which would be expected with the higher area of park per 100km². By examining key Park Facilities (which are usually associated with park quality) across different areas, we found the number of parks with access to qualities within each FUA varied significantly, as shown in **Figure 2**. The quality which was the most common across parks; in all levels of deprivation was

Public Transport, followed by Attractions. With the least common being Toilets and Cafes. There didn't seem to be much variation when it came to different levels of deprivation within the FUA.

Figure 1 Measuring Park size and count across FUAs, categorising by deprivation

Figure 2 Measuring the accessibility to park qualities across FUAs with different deprivation levels (based on the relative index of inequality).

4. Future Work

The analysis so far has allowed us to understand the relevance of current park quality measures; as well as start to understand interactions within the data. Although we have looked at individual objective measures, we hope to combine these to get a more comprehensive understanding into park quality. Future work includes investigating multidimensional aspects of park quality across GB using multivariate clustering methods. This will allow us to understand distinct park typology and their national distribution. In addition, we plan to calculate (using network analysis) neighbourhoods which are within walking distances to park access points, which can then be linked to more granular population and demographics. All outputs will be disseminated and visualised effectively to maximise accessibility to our results. These analyses will allow for the first national assessment of park quality across GB to be completed.

5. Acknowledgements

This project was supported by an NHMRC-UKRI grant application (#GNT1192691). JH, RM and JO are supported by the Medical Research Council [grant number MC_UU_00022/4] and Chief Scientist Office [grant number SPHSU19] at the Places and Health Programme, MRC/CSO Social and Public Health Sciences Unit, University of Glasgow. FC is supported by an MRC Skills Development Fellowship [MR/T027789/1].

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.117976>

Biographies

Jess Hepburn is a Research Associate at MRC/CSO Social and Public Health Sciences Unit within the Places and Health Programme at the University of Glasgow.

Fiona Caryl is a Research Fellow at MRC/CSO Social and Public Health Sciences Unit within the Places and Health Programme at the University of Glasgow.

Jonathan Olsen is a Senior Research Fellow at MRC/CSO Social and Public Health Sciences Unit within the Places and Health Programme at the University of Glasgow.

Rich Mitchell is a Professor at MRC/CSO Social and Public Health Sciences Unit within the Places and Health Programme at the University of Glasgow.